

An Intellectual System to Analyzing Kinetic Motion of Elder in Smart Home

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Abstract- The old age people suffer from diverse uncomfortable factors based on their physical and psychological factors. They may spend huge time inside home; thereby they need an intellectual system to monitor them in that environment. However, intelligent living assistance is anticipated with the use of diverse technologies. A kinetic motion control system makes it probable to improve natural light and adjust luminance based on their characteristics. This work concentrates on light between diverse environmental factors. It is advantageous for mental and physical factors as it may decrease stress and assist in maintaining healthy lives. This kinetic motion system is cast of as architectural factors to manage these functions. The anticipated platform is modeled to diverse scenarios. It comprises of service provisioning manager that gives information regarding environmental factors that describes rules provided for device and sensing information. This may manages determined services. This is considered as a kinetic motion system to validate platform and helpful in managing system through interaction with manager.

I. Introduction

Every human being wants their life to be more sophisticated without the assistance of others. It is essential for all elder people to spend their life in healthier way devoid of help from others [1]. It is essential to huge time in indoor as it s complex to maintain normal life to decline psychological, physical and social acts. The nature of home setup is essential to sense degeneration and physical imbalance and has to be modeled to facilitate lives more independently [2]. Diverse health care, technologies, policies are modeled to respond this crisis. The healthcare paradigm may be shifted to treat diseases to assist prevention and healthy life [3]. This may also provided to reduce essential social costs. Specifically, technologies and social fields are provided by diverse technologies and provide architectural environment [4]. The society growth is accelerating highly and social

cost are measured and assisted for increasing old people. As well, diverse technologies are modeled to resolve this crisis. This model is to enhance the living environment of elder people by merging architectural factors and technologies that may assist significance of elder people based on living assistance [5]. This work concentrates on daytime factors that may offer numerous assistances. Normal light is not so advantageous to mental and physical factors of elder people; as well it may diminish healthy lifestyle and depression [6]. Therefore, this may helps to monitor independent and healthy life by offering indoor environment that raises adjustment of illuminance of elders with weak health condition. Managing natural light to kinetic fades that are related to inside and outside of buildings [7]. This fade may be dynamically changed in real time to environmental factors that uses and facilitates automatic illumination management.

This work concentrates on modeling a system which comprises of reasoning, seasoning, communication and functional interaction to offer indoor illuminance. Sensing is performed as sensing factor and comprises of control and motor modules for examining kinetic motion [8]. The components may collect data from sensors and Wi-Fi to examine façade commands. This may works between kinetic motion and user and cause of an interface for service provisioning based on rules provided and physical factors. At last, the necessity of prototype is based on diverse scenarios. The remainder of the work is modeled as: Section II is related works and background study of proposed model, Section III is proposed model, section IV is numerical results and discussion, section V is conclusion and future research directions.

II. Related works

This section discusses in detail about the modern assistance system that helps in assisting elders. Some research samples of smart homes are used here and some technological services and methods are used over this study. Some essential factors that are related to elder

people and lighting conditions are associated with illumination and so on [9]. The responsive kinetic moves of elder people are monitored and kinds of devices that are related to it are explained. This work derives an object and service for this work [10]. By examining the prevailing technological models and applications for some elder people, this may collect technology and services for system implementation. This work may examines characteristics of old people and factors that influences the natural light are examined based on appropriate illuminance value for indoor environment.

Residential technology for elder people is progressed from diverse architectural guidelines. This may comprise of universal design factors that utilizes Information technology based on smart home technology. Here, there are diverse variations in elder people like walking possibilities, physical variance like diseases, security and health care [11]. In recent times, survey targeting elders may be based independently on AAL, indeed of elders active medical services offered by hospitals that are suggested.

This study is based on intelligent support system and service offered by life time independently over residential environment. This targeted elder may live more independently devoid of any help from others [12]. This work uses sensors and kinetic moves to construct automatic technological system that creates residential environment into better place of leading life [13]. The sensing element may provide body state, object and environmental factors. The elements may transform collected data via knowledge and offer contextual services. This may offer feedback to physical elements and personalized subjects and automatically manages it [14]. Communication elements may connect sensors, actuators and reasoning. At last, intellectual interfaces are provided by mediating systems, humans and services and humans. Based on this definition, AAL needs platform to work, process, combine, analyze and transform collected data to knowledge [15] and to offer service based on situations in reasoning engine.

III. Methodology

The architectural model for providing responsive function may change shape to identify environmental factors as in Fig 1. This kinetic motion elements of buildings where based on changes over environment like organism. This is based on motion envelope which may facilitate actuation of artificial intelligence, sensors, computer program and mechanical factors. There is no aesthetic influence that are expected with constant modification of elements over the environment, however it may show energy consumption that may reduce optimal response with diverse changing factors like buildings.

Fig 1: Elder home monitoring system

As well, energy reduction use may do with optimal response to diverse environmental conditions. It is also probable to enhance elder people comfort in real time. Subsequently, responsive fades may change environment, user need and other functionalities. It may move various devices dynamically based on changing factors in real time and modifies indoor environment. It monitors variations in environmental condition of building fades like epidermis variations. Therefore, certain functions may sense external factors through diverse organs and protect it with changing environmental conditions. It may modify optimization method of environmental condition.

Shading system may shows influencing factors based on natural light and users perspective on natural moves and it needs adjustment techniques with other structures on environmental factors. The kinetic motion is generally modeled by attaching devices to curtain. These moves may respond to diverse environmental factors by kinds of louvers or sunshades that projects to indoor glasses by moving kinetic method. As well, shading system can be adjusted with closing and opening of classifications like folding, rotate, aperture, compress and so on. This kinetic movements of elder people may enhance indoor environment may adjust to certain extent with external factors like heat, light, moisture, sound and so on. It reflects personal functionalities of elder people and it has the ability to provide responsive fade by modifying standardization as in Table I.

Table I: Standardization of elder move

Elder behavior in home		Standardized method	Proposed standard
Living room	General	30-40	75-100
	Recreation	150-200	200-300
	Working	400-600	300-500
	reading	400-600	300-500

Bed room	General	100-150	100-150
	Reading	400-600	750-1000

IV. Numerical results

This section provides the numerical results related to the proposed model. Simulation has been done in MATLAB environment. This may shows the kinetic motion that has to be adjusted based on natural conditions of elder people. This has been modeled with an analysis that responsive kinetic motion is set based on elements surrounding them and by placing the materials.

Table II: Elements related to elderly assistance

Elements	Percentage of devices connected
Outside light	30%
Window	60%
Wall	45%
Ceiling	15%
Floor	15%

Device connected

Fig 2: Connected device

Table III: Kinetic moves

Kinetic moves	Iteration 1	Iteration 2	Iteration 3	Iteration 4
1	640	450	310	440
2	635	410	270	390
3	560	350	220	365
4	450	265	210	285
5	400	245	160	250
6	375	180	125	190
7	260	150	120	120
8	175	75	75	105
9	115	40	35	50
10	25	10	10	20

Fig 3: Kinetic move estimation

Here, the simulation related to kinetic moves is modeled and adjusted with lightening by optimizing light based on standardization. The analysis is done with environmental values to determine target of shading panel. It can be modeled with input values. This is closed length of shading panel while opened completely. This is provided by illumination of indoor values. This work may maintain appropriate illumination without any assistance of light system during various seasons.

From Table II and Table III the numerical values related to kinetic moves are provided and the percentage of connected devices is also estimated over here. The motion estimation of elderly people are demonstrated over here with Iterations 1-4. The percentage of motion estimation is also done to analyze the factors that are more influencing.

V. Conclusion

Growth of population is not a huge issue however it may cause global trends. Here, solutions are provided for age centric factors like support and treatment, however diverse studies may concentrate on elderly significance. Certain prevailing factors comprises of IoT based investigation regarding controlling and monitoring of elder people over residential area. This research work concentrated on a kinetic motion based monitoring of elder people and facilitate them to live independently. This may concentrate in elements of home that are connected to devices. It may holds various components and provide service accordingly. The rules are defined as it is easy and can be changed when modifying components. It is probable to derive service rules that may interfere data by semantic manner. Here, kinetic motion over virtual environment is based on information gathered and service rules managed by physical environment. This may be applicable to kinetic motion system. In future, classifiers are used for segregating the necessary data related to elderly people.

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